

MARKET OF HOUSEHOLD APPLIANCES IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN AND FEATURES OF ITS RESEARCH

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Abstract. In this article, the implementation of new projects, the production of refrigerators, freezers, washing machines, their components and packaging products under the "Artel" and "Samsung" brands, together with a sharp increase in the capacity of existing enterprises, is considered.

Keywords: household appliances, product, brand, refrigerator, washing machines, object, market, demand.

РЫНОК БЫТОВОЙ ТЕХНИКИ В РЕСПУБЛИКЕ УЗБЕКИСТАН И ОСОБЕННОСТИ ЕГО ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматривается реализация новых проектов, производство холодильников, морозильников, стиральных машин, их комплектующих и упаковочной продукции под торговыми марками «Артель» и «Самсунг» совместно с резким увеличением мощностей действующих предприятий. .

Ключевые слова: бытовая техника, товар, бренд, холодильник, стиральные машины, объект, рынок, спрос.

INTRODUCTION

In order to study the state of marketing research in the research object, it is necessary to have an idea about the current state and development prospects of this field in the Republic. Refrigerators and freezers are among the sophisticated household appliances, and they have their own market and their own stores. The peculiarity of this market is that the demand in it has a high level of elasticity and is directly related to the income and standard of living of the population. In this regard, the stability of the market depends on the indicators of social development of the population of Uzbekistan.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

According to the data, Uzbekistan has 1046-4125 dollars per capita. located in the group of countries with the level of income (GDP) (low-middle income). The task until 2030 is 4126-12745 dollars per capita. is to achieve a level of development that allows comparison with countries with income (upper-middle income). This can only be achieved through a radical improvement in competitiveness, leading to dramatic economic growth, because to "catch up" to this group, it is necessary to solve the development issues that involve both catching up and surpassing at the same time.

Sharp economic growth implies changing the current economic growth model based on the development of fuel and energy, chemistry, metallurgy and other basic sectors of the economy to a growth model based on the advanced development of processing industries. This can be ensured only in the conditions of competition, which encourages enterprises to achieve the effective scale of production (the maximum volume of products in the conditions of minimum resources). Until the 90s of the 20th century, there was no competition in Uzbekistan due to the state monopoly in all areas, which is a characteristic feature of the planned economy.

With the beginning of economic reforms, it was implemented in the following ways to create a competitive environment:

a) introduction of private property, as well as state expropriation and privatization procedure;

b) removing monopolies from industries by reorganizing large enterprises;

c) formation of the small business and private entrepreneurship (KBXT) sector;

g) introduction of economic mechanisms in commodity and financial markets.

"Uzeltexanoat" joint-stock company is entrusted with the tasks of saturating the consumer market with household appliances and developing the industry in this field.

RESULTS

Thanks to the conditions and facilities created during the years of independence, the number of enterprises belonging to the system of the joint-stock company "Uzeltexanoat", the type and volume of products, and the export volume have increased several times. In particular, the production of a number of household appliances, such as gas and electric stoves, vacuum cleaners, televisions, air conditioners, and refrigerators, which are necessary for everyday life, has been mastered. Technical cooperation with leading companies of countries such as South Korea, China, and the USA was carried out, and production of products under their world-famous brands was achieved. According to the analysis, the share of household appliances in total products increased from 13.7 percent in 2016 to 40 percent in 2021. Several projects in this direction are being implemented this year.

Currently, 10 enterprises producing more than 2,000 types of cable and wire products, 21 enterprises producing more than 25 types of household appliances, and 16 enterprises providing technical services are working effectively within the company. If in 2016 the volume of product production in the network is 80 bln. amounted to 1 trillion soums in 2021. 330 billion amounted to soum. Last year and in the first half of this year, system enterprises spent 1.5 trillion. more than soums of products were delivered to energy, oil and gas, mining industries and social sector facilities of our republic. Products of 47 enterprises are exported to Central Asia, CIS and other countries.

It should be noted separately that production of products on a local basis is a factor of economic growth, as well as saving and reducing costs for raw materials and imported goods. 1 billion in the industry by 2030. It is expected that an investment of about USD 100,000 will be used, and the production of 22 types of products that did not exist before will be launched, and the volume of product preparation will increase by 5.1 times due to the modernization of all enterprises.

In the fulfillment of these tasks, it is of great importance to implement new projects together with a sharp increase in the capacity of existing enterprises. One of them is the "Artel" household appliances production project.

Among the enterprises operating under the "Artel" trademark are "POLARIS TECHNOLOGIES" and "INDIGO ELECTRONICS" joint ventures in the form of a limited liability company with the production of refrigerators, freezers, washing machines, their components and packaging products under the "Artel" and "Samsung" brands. are engaged in. There is a service center, its branches are located in all regions of our republic. Cooperation has been established with Samsung of South Korea, Embraco of Brazil, Midea of the People's Republic of China and other world-famous companies. In order to expand the scale of production

of refrigerators and coolers, a project with the capacity to remove an additional 50,000 such products from the conveyor was implemented this year.

The content of marketing research is based on the functions of the product in the market and its place in human life. The peculiarity of sophisticated household appliances is that they have the ability to change the ideas of housekeeping and the principles of housekeeping. This feature not only affects the forms, methods and goals of marketing research in the market, but also determines their content.

As for the uniqueness of the household appliances market, we can point out the following special aspects of it:

- Focusing on the technical indicators of products on the market. Since the products are designed to serve for a long time, the consumer pays attention to their technical capabilities in the first place.
- The importance of the period of use of the product and its reliability during this period. Since household appliances are expensive products, operating costs and their guarantees are also very important for the consumer.
- The importance of brands and trademarks in the household appliances market. The manufacturer's reputation and image is a key indicator of product competitiveness and has a major impact on purchasing decisions.
- The inclusion of provision of household appliances as one of the main indicators of the standard of living of the population leads to the basis of the principles arising from the number of the population in the assessment of its capacity.
- The need for household appliances is closely related to the ratio of population strata. It is no exaggeration to say that the level of population stratification determines the composition of the demand in this market.

DISCUSSION

Based on the characteristics of the products in the household appliances market, it can be divided into several sub-markets, namely, the market of refrigerators and freezers, the market of air conditioners, the market of washing machines, the market of vacuum cleaners, the market of irons and dryers, the market of microwave ovens and ovens, the market of television and video equipment. and hokazos.

Each of these sub-markets will have its own characteristics along with common characteristics. This is because household appliances are used for different purposes, in different life situations and by different groups of consumers. Therefore, consumer representatives in this market can be considered separately.

In this regard, in the theory of marketing research, methods and tools for studying the market of household appliances and durable consumer goods have been developed.

These methods are divided into the following main groups according to their accuracy and the tools used:

- Standard method. At the basis of this method, consumption norms formed in society are taken as a basis, and when studying the consumer market, it is based on the assumption that each buyer strives for an average social norm. For example, based on statistical data, information about the fact that 86% of families in our country have refrigerators today, every new family tries to buy a refrigerator, it has become a primary need for a family that does not have this

product, families that have a refrigerator need to get a second refrigerator or upgrade it. based on its existence. The normative method includes sanitary-hygienic norms, technical norms, economic norms and social-psychological norms.

- Technical and economic method. The basis of this method is the presence of effective service life of each product and the life cycle of the product in consumption. For example, the warranty period of a television is three years, and the operational life is considered to be approximately ten years (if the development of transmission technologies is not taken into account). So, after an average of ten years, any TV will have to be replaced. The presence of a strong correlation between the economic status of the family and the demand for household appliances is also a positive motivation for the use of this method.
- Method of social change. In this method, the behavior of buyers in the market is determined by family and collective factors. For example, the demand for information is causing the use of television to rise to the level of social need. In addition, it is possible to forecast the demand for televisions under the influence of family growth, separation of new families, differences in the wishes of family members and other factors.
- Method of social surveys. This method is one of the unique forms of traditional marketing research methods, which serves to reveal or clarify undefined market laws in the above methods.

The use of the above methods serves to determine and analyze static and dynamic indicators of the capacity, composition, capacity in the household appliances market. In addition, it is necessary to use other quantitative and qualitative methods of marketing research to determine the position and competitiveness of a specific enterprise or brand.

When conducting marketing research on the market, two sources of information are used to obtain information - primary and secondary. Secondary sources are existing data that always need to be studied first. In most cases, these data are collected for purposes other than the intended research areas. Therefore, it is necessary to collect new data or fill them with primary data. The difference between the sources of information has led to the existence of two different concepts - desk research and field research outside the office. Cabinet research consists of analyzing secondary data and adapting them to the company's goals. For example,

There are several ways to collect primary data: observation, visualization, experiment.

Using the observation method, the researcher can gather information about the changes in demand for the product of interest by gathering around buyers and sellers. In the same way, it is possible to collect information about competitors' products.

It is important to use it when creating new product classifications, creating advertising texts, using mass media in advertising, preparing for sales promotion activities, researching product movement channels, etc. This method is between observation and experiment.

With the help of an experiment, some factors of the thing being studied and their influence on its change are determined. The purpose of this method is to reject the working hypotheses. This method of data collection is used to determine the best way to train sales personnel, to study marketing problems such as determining the level of evaluation.

CONCLUSIONS

The fact that there are divisions in the structure of the above methods should be used in the organization of marketing research in the household appliances market of production

enterprises. In this regard, a thorough study and use of research methods by the marketing staff of enterprises has become an urgent task today.

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